

D.3.2 POLICY BRIEF:

“POWERING EQUALITY: AN INTERSECTIONAL APPROACH TO GENDER-SENSITIVE CAREERS IN THE ENERGY SECTOR AND ENERGY TRANSFORMATION”

WP3 – Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance Women in Energy Transition

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Policy Brief: Powering Equality: An Intersectional Approach to Gender-Sensitive Careers in the Energy Sector and Energy Transformation

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Introduction

The green and digital transitions are reshaping Europe's energy landscape, creating unprecedented demand for new skills, interdisciplinary expertise, and diverse talent. At the same time, the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020–2025, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the ERA Policy Agenda underline the obligation to promote equality, non-discrimination, and inclusive labour markets across all sectors. Despite these commitments, the energy sector continues to be shaped by persistent gender inequalities, structural biases, and cultural norms that limit women's participation and advancement. Women's opportunities, constraints, and pathways into the energy sector are shaped by the intersection of multiple identities—including socio-economic background, geography, ethnicity, disability, disciplinary identity (STEM vs. SSH), and family status. Achieving a just energy transformation requires more than increasing the number of women in classrooms or workplaces. It demands deep structural change across educational institutions, labour markets, leadership structures and societal norms.

This policy brief applies an intersectional lens to evidence from focus group interviews and national workshops conducted within the gEneSys project with students, academics, industry professionals, and public officials across Germany, Italy, Poland, and the UK¹. It synthesises barriers, enablers and structural conditions needed to ensure inclusive participation in the emerging energy landscape. It provides evidence-based recommendations to support EU institutions, Member States, higher education institutions, and industry stakeholders in advancing intersectional and gender-sensitive policies in the energy domain.

Main Results from Interviews and Workshops

Structural and Cultural Barriers in Education and Skills Development

- **Early socialisation shapes career aspirations long before university.** Participants described how girls are taught (explicitly or subtly) to avoid technical fields, discouraged from risk-taking, and often praised for compliance rather than ambition.

¹ An extended report from the focus group interviews and workshops can be found here: [D.3.3 - Analyses of and Recommendations for Training Programmes on Gender-Sensitive Energy Transition](#)

- **Stereotypes**—sometimes disguised as “protective” attitudes—continue to influence family choices, teacher expectations, and employer behaviour.
- Across energy-related higher education, gender is largely absent as a topic of study or a structural priority. Students frequently described their programmes as “**gender-neutral or gender-blind**”, noting the lack of explicit integration of gender analysis in curricula or classroom discussions. Gender content, when present, was occasionally introduced by individual lecturers as part of broader themes such as energy justice but was not institutionalised within teaching structures. This absence contributes to low awareness among students of gendered dynamics in the energy labour market.

Barriers to Career Entry and Progression

- **Discipline:** Social science profiles—often including many women—are undervalued despite their relevance for system transition and citizen engagement.
- **Cultural norms**, including the perception of energy-related professions as male domain and expectations in some cultural groups that undermine women's authority in technical fields.
- **Information gap on career opportunities in energy-sector.**
- **Territorial disparities** (e.g., between metropolitan and peripheral regions) influence access to internships, training, and job opportunities.
- **Workplace safety and stereotypes:** Women face biased assumptions about physical ability, risk tolerance, or suitability for fieldwork, particularly in nuclear or conventional energy settings.
- **Maternity and care responsibilities** can stall progression when flexibility or institutional supports are lacking.
- **Meritocracy rhetoric** in some national contexts obscures structural inequalities, framing gender-targeted measures as illegitimate despite evidence of implicit bias in recruitment and assessment.
- **Male-dominated professional networks** and informal decision-making channels impede women's advancement and visibility
- Lack of gender parity reduces the likelihood of cultural change; evidence indicates that a **critical mass of at least 30% women** is necessary to shift norms

For women facing compounded marginalisation (e.g., ethnic minority women, women with disabilities, first-generation graduates), these barriers are intensified.

Enablers of Inclusion and Participation

Across countries, key enablers include:

- **Women in leadership positions**—both in academia and industry—serve as powerful **role models** and help legitimize women’s presence in male-dominated areas.
- **Interdisciplinary programmes** that bridge STEM and SSH, making the field more accessible to a wider range of students.
- **Practical experience** (internships, labs, international placements) which is particularly critical for students lacking professional networks.
- **Supportive supervisors, partners/family members, or teachers** who actively counter stereotypes.
- **Transparent hiring and promotion systems**, which reduce discretionary bias.
- **Organisational policies** addressing gender, care responsibilities, generation, and diversity, not merely tokenistic quotas.

Policy Recommendations

Recommendations for EU Institutions

- Mainstream intersectional gender analysis across **energy, skills, cohesion, and digitalisation policies** (e.g., Green Deal, REPowerEU, European Skills Agenda).
- Promote disaggregated data collection (gender, age, disability, socio-economic background, migration background, geography) in EU-funded projects and national monitoring.
- Develop EU-wide guidance for **gender-responsive and inclusive green skills strategies**.

Recommendations for Member States

- Integrate intersectional gender equality objectives into **National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs)** and **national skills strategies**.

- Strengthen support for women from disadvantaged regions through targeted scholarships, mobility schemes, and mentoring initiatives.
- Support regional partnerships linking education providers, companies, and public authorities to reduce territorial inequalities.
- Encourage companies to adopt **transparent, inclusive recruitment and promotion frameworks, including reporting on gender pay gap and promotion rates.**
- Demonstrate visible, sustained **national-level commitment to initiatives promoting gender equality** in the energy system to raise the awareness and build the broad societal support for meaningful change.
- Implement **national-level grants, incubators, and entrepreneurship programmes** to support women-led start-ups and innovation projects in energy sector.
- Integrate **gender equality into primary and secondary education curricula**, challenging stereotypes about technical careers and providing early exposure to energy sector.

Recommendations for Higher Education Institutions

- Embed gender equality and intersectionality across STEM and energy-related programmes, including through compulsory modules and case studies.
- Increase female representation in senior academic and administrative positions.
- Establish new interdisciplinary programmes and **fields** (e.g., Systems Transition Engineering) that integrate engineering, social sciences, and policy studies, where gender, intersectionality, and sustainability are embedded from inception.
- Provide flexible learning pathways for students balancing study, work, or caregiving responsibilities.
- Support women's networks to exchange knowledge and advocacy.

Recommendations for Companies and Industry Actors

- Implement evidence-based dynamic equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) strategies aligned with EU standards and intersectional principles, including targets, timelines, monitoring and accountability mechanisms.
- Ensure transparent career progression, objective evaluation criteria, and gender-balanced selection panels.

- Provide flexible working conditions and comprehensive support for employees with caring responsibilities (parental leave, hybrid work, adjusted working hours, return-to-work programmes following long-term leaves).
- Develop inclusive professional networks and mentoring schemes for underrepresented groups.
- Challenge workplace stereotypes about women's capability for technical and field-based roles through targeted awareness campaign and evidence-based job design.

Recommendations for Civil Society and Local Authorities

- Promote energy literacy initiatives targeting women and marginalised communities.
- Strengthen participatory governance in local renewable energy projects.
- Facilitate partnerships between NGOs, schools, and municipalities to support inclusive career awareness.

Conclusions

Achieving gender equality in the energy sector requires coordinated actions across all levels – from the EU policy frameworks to national strategies, industry, educational institutions and civil society practices. Without intentional interventions, structural and cultural barriers will continue to limit women's participation in this sector. Success depends on three pillars: systemic change through gender-sensitive policies and data collection, educational transformation and inclusive workplace cultures. With the energy transition accelerating, embedding gender equality as a core principle is not only a matter of justice but also innovation.

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